

THE PLACE AND IMPORTANCE OF ISCED (International Standard Classification of Education) OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Annotation: This article analyzes the role of ISCED (International Standard Classification of Education) in the preschool education system and the importance of using assessment systems that comply with international standards in the preschool education system.

Keywords: International standards, ISCED, preschool education, preschool education organizations, leadership, international experience, pedagogical management

In today's globalization environment, international standards, quality assurance mechanisms, and new approaches to assessing leaders are developing rapidly in the field of education. Therefore, improving the qualification of leading personnel of preschool educational organizations and improving their certification system based on international standards is one of the urgent tasks. The large-scale fundamental reforms being carried out in the preschool education system in new Uzbekistan require a review of the mechanisms for assessing and certifying the professional competence of leading personnel of preschool educational organizations. The director of a preschool educational organization is considered not only a person who carries out administrative management, but also a leader who organizes the pedagogical process, develops the team, and introduces innovative ideas. Therefore, it is important to form a certification system that determines the qualification level of leading personnel of preschool educational organizations based on clear criteria, stimulates their professional development, and meets international standards. In many countries of the world, unique models of assessment and certification of leading personnel of preschool educational organizations have been formed, which are carried out on the basis of a competency-based approach, with the participation of independent assessment organizations, diagnosis of professional and practical skills, and a transparent and fair system. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev consistently continues fundamental reforms in this area, and the attention paid to the development of the network of preschool educational organizations in accordance with modern requirements and standards, their reconstruction and modernization also has a noble goal: to ensure that the owners of our future grow up no less than anyone else and become worthy successors to their great ancestors. The effective functioning of preschool educational organizations directly affects the physical, mental and social development of children. Therefore, improving the professional qualifications of preschool educational leaders and bringing them into line with international standards is an urgent issue. In recent years, research has been expanding on strengthening the decision-making and management skills of preschool educational organizations' leaders through the study of successful education systems of different countries, the implementation of international experiences, and the introduction of accredited training programs. Approaches to assessment, developed on the basis of international standards, allow preschool educational organizations' leaders to effectively manage the

organization, transform the pedagogical process, and improve the quality of education. At the same time, constant study and exchange of international experiences allow preschool educational organizations' leaders to adapt to modern pedagogical requirements and apply new strategies in their pedagogical activities.

Ensuring the compliance of pedagogical personnel with the requirements of the International Standard Classification of Education, improving the system of monitoring, evaluation and strategic planning of the labor market, including its professional and qualification structure, and meeting the current and prospective need for qualified personnel, taking into account the application of new progressive technologies in practice, has been set as a priority task

ISCED (International Standard Classification of Education) is a standard developed by UNESCO and internationally accepted for the classification of education systems. The main task of ISCED is to provide an opportunity to describe, compare and statistically analyze the education systems of different countries based on a single criterion.

ISCED (International Classification of Education Levels) - systematizes education into nine main areas, each area is designated by a special name and number. This approach makes it possible to standardize educational stages, compare them internationally, and determine the qualifications of teachers and leaders.

Each level has its own goals and directions, covering all stages of education from preschool to doctoral level.

1. ISCED 0: Pre-primary education;
2. ISCED 1: Primary education;
3. ISCED 2: Secondary education;
4. ISCED 3: Upper secondary education;
5. ISCED 4: Post-secondary, non-tertiary education;
6. ISCED 5: Short-term higher education programmes;
7. ISCED 6: Bachelor's degree;
8. ISCED 7: Master's degree;
9. ISCED 8: Doctorate or PhD degree.

In conclusion, it can be said that by adapting the leaders of preschool educational organizations to international experiences and international assessment standards, their decision-making, pedagogical strategy formulation, and management skills can be systematically and effectively developed.

REFERENCES

1. UNESCO Institute for Statistics. (2012). *International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED 2011)*.

2.UNESCO. (2014). *ISCED Fields of Education and Training 2013 (ISCED-F 2013): Detailed Field Descriptions*.

3.Akter, S., & Hasan, M. M. (2024). Revolutionizing kindergarten education: a comprehensive review of teachers' challenges and solutions. Available at SSRN 5071967.

https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=5071967

4.Jing, Z. (2025). The Evolution, Present Practices, and Future Directions of Early Childhood Education and Care in China. *European Journal of Education*, 60(1), e12880.

<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/ejed.12880>

